

SPECTRUM ANALYSIS OF MINERAL CONTENTS OF FRUITS.

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Using a high frequency spark discharge of the type employed by Walther and Werner Gerlach in their study of biological specimens, the mineral contents of mangoes, plantains, grapes, oranges and apples have been investigated spectroscopically. It has been shown that in the epicarp, mesocarp and endocarp of the same fruit the mineral contents are different, and the conclusion is drawn that generally the outer covering of a fruit is richer than the interior in calcium, magnesium, manganese and silicon.

In recent years the use of the spectrograph in the field of chemical analysis, both qualitative and quantitative, has opened up new avenues of research. As a result of the investigations carried out in many laboratories, it is now clear that the amounts of the minor metallic elements in a given sample can be estimated without recourse to special apparatus. The accuracy of the determination is, however, subject to rather a wide variation, though even in unfavourable circumstances, one can easily distinguish between 0.01, 0.1 and 1%. As a balance against this latitude in accuracy, the estimation is rapid, and a permanent record of the mineral content is obtained. There are in practice several methods of exciting the material under investigation to radiate. The Lundegardh's flame spectrum method of quantitative spectrographic analysis has been principally employed for successful analysis of solutions and soils. Other methods such as the electric arc or the high tension spark are also available for qualitative as well as quantitative analysis. Sundara Rao using treated samples in the arc has examined spectroscopically some fertile and infertile sugarcane soils (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, VI B., 91); the fertility of the soil has been traced to minute traces of zinc, manganese and titanium. Representative types of cereals, pulses and leafy vegetables have also been spectroscopically examined by the same author (*Science & Culture*, 1938, 4, 362; *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 351) for trace elements. By discovering new methods of exciting radiation, practically any substance may be subjected to spectroscopic analysis. In attempts to identify the mineral content in organic substances, the carbon arc method is unsuitable on account of the difficulty in obtaining pure carbon rods free from metallic traces. The Lundegardh's flame method is equally inapplicable if the organic substance is to be examined directly without further treatment. The high frequency method of discharge gives an intense source free from

such disadvantages. The high frequency source employed by Walther and Werner Gerlach ("Clinical and Pathological Applications of Spectrum Analysis" Eng. Ed., Adam Hilger Ltd.) for the analysis of biological specimens, like skin, gallstones, bones etc. is eminently suited for the examination of all organic matter. Spectroscopic methods have been employed for the analysis of biological fluids for heavy metals (Armstrong and Brackett, *J. Ind. Hyg. Toxicol.*, **21**, 446) for determining the magnesium content in blood in various diseases (Zimmer, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1939, **1**, 93) for finding the metallic nutritional requirements of yeast (Richards and Trontman, *J. Bact.*, 1940, **39**, 739) and allied problems. In the present investigation the mineral contents of the different parts of a number of fruits have been investigated by the high frequency spark method; this method can also be used with success in the case of soils, salts, metal foils, metal deposits and ores.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Both the high and the low frequency currents traverse the spark gap when the ordinary condenser arrangement is employed. The spark gap system was arranged so as to eliminate the low frequency oscillation by means of a small capacity in series. The metallic deposit on one side of a glass plate was connected to one terminal of the secondary of a Tesla transformer and the other terminal connected to a platinum wire (0.2-0.8 mm. thick). The fruit material which was being examined was placed on the unmetallised side of the glass plate with the platinum wire tip only a few millimetres above the specimen. The radiation from the spark was focussed by a quartz lens on to the slit of a Hilger quartz spectrograph. Using hypersensitive panchromatic plates, intense spectra between 7000 and 2000Å were recorded with exposures of the order of one minute. The fruit and the skin sections were freshly obtained each time and no

previous treatments were given. The specimen was placed on a filter paper moistened with a 10% sodium nitrate solution and during the exposure the occasional addition of this solution prevented the burning of the sample. When the spark had consumed the portion directly below the electrode, the specimen could be moved so as to bring the other parts into the discharge. Several varieties of mango, orange, apple, grape and plantain were examined. In each case the epicarp (skin) and mesocarp (fruit) have been separately studied. In a few cases the endocarp (seed) has also been subjected to spectroscopic examination.

Various methods have been employed in quantitative spectrum analysis. For instance, in the method due to Lockyer the amount of the element is estimated by the "length" of a spark line". The progressive disappearance of certain lines or the order of their "persistence" as a method in analysis was introduced by Hartley. The method of estimating the abundance by relative intensities of lines, estimated either visually or photometrically, introduced first by de Gramont is widely employed.

In the present work the relative estimates of an element in the various parts of a fruit are given on the basis of the order of "persistence" of the lines of the element in the various spectra as well as of the eye estimates of the relative intensities of the lines employing the "internal standard method". The determination of the abundance of the elements by the order of "persistence" of lines is made with the aid of the data supplied by Twymann ("Wavelength Tables for Spectrum Analysis") and by Smith ("Visual Lines for Spectrum Analysis"). As sodium nitrate solution was employed for rendering the spark gap conducting as

TABLE I.

Mango (*Mangifera indica*, Linn.).

Varieties examined: Mulgova, Rasapuri, Neelam, Tootapuri. (Fig. 1).

	Conc. of element % by wt.			Remarks.
	Epicarp.	Mesocarp.	Endocarp.	
Ca	>0.1	0.01	0.1	{ In Tootapuri (skin) Ca content is less than the figure given here.
Cu	0.001	—	—	Cu is absent in Tootapuri and in Neelam.
Mg	0.1	0.01	0.1	
Mn	0.005	—	—	{ In varieties other than Mulgova Mn content is less than the figure given.
Si	0.1	—	—	{ Si content is higher in Mulgova than in other varieties.
St	0.01	—	—	

well as for cooling the specimen, sodium has not been included in the list of elements. Using dilute hydrochloric acid or potassium nitrate solution, however, the abundance of sodium could be estimated. Further work is in progress and from the preliminary results so far obtained, we are giving below only the abundance of those elements which exist to the extent of 0.001 or higher percent. In all the tables concentration refers to percentage by weight.

TABLE II.

Orange (*Citrus aurantium*, Linn.)
Variety—Coorg.

	Conc. of element		
	Epicarp.	Skin covering mesocarp.	Mesocarp.
Ca	>0.01	0.01	>0.001
Cu	—	0.007	—
Mg	0.1	0.1	<0.1
Sr	0.01	0.001	—

TABLE IV.

Grape (*Vitis vinifera*, Linn.)
Varieties—Black and Kabul.

	Conc. of elements.	
	Epicarp.	Mesocarp.
Ca	>0.01	>0.001
Cu.*	0.001	—
Mg	0.1	<0.1
Sr	0.001	—

* Cu is present only in Kabul variety and not in black variety.

TABLE III.

Apple (*Pyrus malus*, Linn.)
Variety—Bangalore.

	Conc. of elements.	
	Epicarp.	Mesocarp.
Ca	0.001	<0.001
Mg	0.01	0.001

TABLE V.

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca* Linn.)
Varieties examined—Rasabale,
Pacchabale, and Rajabale.

	Conc. of elements.	
	Epicarp.	Mesocarp.
Ca †	0.001	<0.001
Mg ‡	0.001	<0.001
Si	0.1	—

† In Rajabale (skin) Ca content is higher than in other variety.

‡ In Rasabale (fruit) Mg content is higher than in other varieties.

On the basis of the above figures it must be concluded that in the fruits examined calcium, magnesium and silicon contents are generally higher in the epicarp than in the mesocarp.